

BIOCOMPATIBLE NANOCOMPOSITE FILMS BASED ON SERICIN- MODIFIED DIALDEHYDE CARBOXYMETHYLCELLULOSE CONTAINING SILVER NANOPARTICLES

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The development of biocompatible and environmentally safe nanocomposite materials based on renewable biopolymers is of growing interest in biomedical applications. Among natural polymers, dialdehyde carboxymethylcellulose (DACMC) is a highly reactive polysaccharide that can form stable polymeric matrices, while silk sericin — a protein derived from silk industry waste — exhibits notable biological activity, including antioxidant and antimicrobial properties.

In this study, a graft copolymer matrix composed of DACMC and sericin was synthesized and utilized as a template for the in situ generation of silver nanoparticles (AgNPs). The incorporation of sericin into the DACMC network improved biocompatibility and provided functional groups facilitating the uniform nucleation and stabilization of AgNPs.

The optical properties of the resulting nanocomposite films were examined using UV-Vis spectroscopy, which revealed a distinct plasmon resonance band at 400–500 nm, confirming the reduction of Ag^+ ions to metallic Ag^0 nanoparticles. X-ray diffraction analysis indicated the crystalline nature of AgNPs with characteristic reflections at $2\theta \approx 8.1^\circ$, 44.9° , and 65.8° , corresponding to (111), (200), and (220) lattice planes. Scanning electron microscopy demonstrated homogeneously dispersed spherical and needle-like nanoparticles ranging from 30 to 90 nm in size, well stabilized within the polymeric matrix.

The results confirm that the DACMC/sericin biopolymer system provides an efficient and eco-friendly route for the fabrication of uniform and stable silver nanoparticle-based nanocomposite films. Such materials are promising for biomedical and pharmaceutical applications, particularly in the development of antimicrobial coatings, wound dressings, and bioactive packaging systems.

References

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